

Management of Osteoarticular Infection by Different Treatment Options

Asad Ali Chaudhry, Syed Asif Ali Shah, Akkad Rafique, Muhammad Iqbal, Nadia Sultan, Sana Kamran Hussain, Amna Shahab, Muhammad Mudassar Mehmood, Chaudhry Ahmad Khan, Shahid Majeed

ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: Osteo-articular infections (OI) are a common problem and challenging for Orthopedic Surgeons. The consequences can be local manifestations to a systemic infection or limb loss. Accurate diagnosis is necessary for good treatment and control the drastic consequences. Conventional treatment may require antibiotics for prolonged duration according to culture and sensitivity. Our study objective was to determine osteo-articular infection and the effectiveness of treatment modalities.

Place & duration of study: This study was a case series done at the Department of Orthopedic Surgery KEMU / Mayo Hospital, Lahore from December 2010 to March 2013.

Methods: We included 200 hemodynamically stable patients 18 to 55 years of age of either gender with osteo-articular infection. They were diagnosed on history, clinical examination both local and systemic, previous treatment, previous surgical procedure and baseline included CBC, ESR, CRP, LFT's with albumin, globulin, RFT's, blood sugar random, affected joint radiographs, pus & soft tissue culture sensitivity, CT scan and MRI. We managed all patients both medically and surgically who presented with infection of bone and joint due to trauma, hospital acquired infection or due to hematogenous spread. We followed patients in out-patient department for six months and observed the post-operative treatment outcomes.

Results: Out of the total 200 patients, majority 172 (86%) were male and 28 (14%) were female. Lower limb infection was observed in 128 (64%) patients, while 46 (23%) patients had upper limb infection, and 27 (13.5%) patients had septic arthritis of lower limb. Treatment outcomes were observed and there were excellent outcomes in 31 (15.5%) patients, good in 56 (28%), fair in 69 (34.5%) and poor in 43 (21.5%) patients.

Conclusion: Staphylococcus aureus is the most common causative organism of osteoarticular infection. Males are predominantly affected. Antibiotic regime for 03 weeks according to culture and sensitivity is the most effective treatment in conjunction with surgical wound debridement, curettage, arthrotomy, sequestrectomy and exchange of infected prosthesis show favourable outcomes.

Keywords: Osteo-articular Infection, Antibiotics, Culture and Sensitivity, Trauma

INTRODUCTION

Osteo-articular infection remains a frightening challenge for decades. It leads to psychological stress for the patient, their families and associated healthcare expenditures, morbidity and mortality.¹ Bacterial growth in joint may lead to inflammation and results in joint destruction.² The exact cause of the acute osteomyelitis remains challenging. Bacterial cause is treated without considering other causes of osteoarticular infections.³ Gram positive bacteria are commonly found in osteo-articular infection (OI) and Gram-negative bacteria accounts for 10% to 23% osteo-articular infection (OI).^{4,6} With the advancement of antibiotics and added effect of surgical management there is approximately 20-30% long term recurrence rate.⁷ Despite advances in antibiotic therapy and modern devices, the complexity in the medical and surgical management of osteo-articular infection (OI) is a challenge in adults whereas in children, there is little high-quality evidence for management of bone and joint infection available.⁸ We were not able to explore the impact of hospital acquired infection and its effects on patient's hospital stay, economic burden, choice and duration of

antibiotics and infection associated patient morbidity in orthopedic patients. Infection after joint replacement is associated with high cost, morbidity and mortality. In most cases there required removal of prosthesis. It costs \$50,000 per patient and \$250 million per annum in United States.^{9,10}

With this aim, we planned this study to assess the prospective treatment outcome of osteo-articular infections.

METHODOLOGY

This case series was done at the Department of Orthopedic Surgery KEMU / Mayo Hospital, Lahore from December 2010 to March 2013. A total of 200 hemodynamically stable patients of all ages of either gender with osteo-articular infection were treated. They were diagnosed on history, clinical examination both local and systemic, previous treatment, surgical procedure and baseline included CBC, ESR, CRP, LFT's with albumin, globulin, RFT's, blood sugar random, pus & soft tissue culture sensitivity. Affected joint radiographs, CT scan and MRI were included in the radiological investigations supporting the diagnosis of osteoarticular infection. All patients were managed on both medical and surgical treatment who presented with joint infection due to trauma, hospital acquired infection and hematogenous route. We excluded all patients who

Correspondence: Dr. Asad Ali Chaudhry
Associate Professor
Department of Orthopedic Surgery
CMH Lahore Medical College
E-mail: drasadch@gmail.com

were previously diagnosed and had started treatment for osteo-articular infection previously.

After approval from the ethical board of the university, informed written consent was obtained from all the patients. Patients who visited the out-patient department (OPD), accident and emergency department or admitted in the ward were included in the study. The questionnaire was specifically designed after reading literature, books and later finalized by the supervisor was used a tool for data collection and subsequent analysis. Clinical diagnostic criteria included: history of +/-fever, limp, inability to bear weight on affected limb, localized pain on palpation or point tenderness to pressure, expanding to distal or proximal ends of the bone, increased temperature when compared with normal joint, open wound with or without pus /discharge on clinical examination. +/- Elevated ESR, positive CRP, positive culture and sensitivity and on radiograph, CT scan and MRI findings supportive to clinical evaluation were labelled as Osteo-articular infection.

The outcome was measured both clinically and radiologically. We compared the osteo-articular infection with age, gender, duration of operation, delay in treatment, and length of hospital stay, prophylactic use and duration of antibiotics, underlying patient disease and other pertinent variables. We followed patients post-operatively in OPD at one-week intervals. They were called in for follow up visits till alleviation of local sign and symptoms of infection were observed and satisfactory.

Data was entered and later analyzed using into SPSS 20.0. We presented categorical variable as rates, ratio and frequency. Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation; We used the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test to see that Osteo-articular infections are same on the average in different types of diseases. The association of the osteo-articular infection with age, gender, duration of operation, delay in treatment, and length of hospital stay, prophylactic use and timing of antibiotics, underlying patient disease and other pertinent variables that can influence the osteo-articular infections by using multiple logistic regression & multivariate analyses.

RESULTS

Out of the total 200 patients, male were 172 (86%) and female were 28 (14%). Open fractures were graded according to Gustilo classification and there were 97 (76.4%) grade-I patients, grade-II was 23 (18.1%) patients, and grade-III were 7 (5.5%) patients in our study.

139 (69.5%) patients had history of operation. The onset was insidious in 35 (17.5%) patients. Past history of fever was present in 67 (33.5%) patients. Only 62 (31%) patients had systemic illness. Males were found to be

more affected than females due to increased incidence of trauma in men. The patients presenting with previous surgical procedures included Open reduction internal fixation (ORIF) in 52 (37.4%) patients and CRIF in 19 (13.7%) patients. External fixator was applied in 56 (40.3%) patients, 02 (1.4%) had Austin Moore prosthesis (AMP), 01 (0.7%) had total hip arthroplasty (THA), 05 (3.6%) had arthroscopy and 04 (2.9%) had amputation of the limb.

Amongst total, the 56 cases with external fixator, we applied Dynamic Compression plate (DCP) in 37 (27.4%) patients, K-wires in 19 (14.1%), DHS in 09 (6.7%), cannulated screw fixation in 05 (3.7%) and 05 (3.7%) had broad Dynamic Compression plate (DCP). In 02 (1.5%) Austin Moore Prosthesis (AMP) was done, and 01 (0.7%) total hip arthroplasty (THA) was done.

Swelling was observed in 14 (07%) patients and 186 (93%) had no swelling during their hospital stay. Most 186 (93%) patients were discharged after short specific period of the surgery and 14 (07%) had long hospital stay due to various complications. Out of total 200 patients, only 24 (12%) had restriction at proximal and distal joint. Most 11 (5.5%) has proximal joint restriction and 13 (6.5%) had restriction at distal joint. Weight bearing was noted and most 67 (33.5%) had full weight bearing, 57 (28.5%) had partial weight bearing, 74 (37%) were unable to bear the full weight and only 02 (01%) were bedridden in our study.

Neurovascular deficit was evaluated before they were enrolled in the study and 07 (3.5%) had distal neurological and only 04 (02%) had vascular deficit in our study. We obtained complete blood count and c-reactive protein at different intervals during follow-up and measured as baseline till 24th week after surgery. Only 70 (35%) patients had positive C-reactive protein (CRP) (> 6 mg/dl) at baseline visit. Out of 70 patients, the C-reactive protein level was (> 6 mg/dl) in 48 (24%) patient after 1st week with progressive standard treatment, 32 (16%) at third week, 14 (07%) patients at 6th week follow-up and only 02 (01%) had positive CRP after 24th week of treatment. Pre-operative mean albumin was 3.4±0.43mg/dl. At follow-up of 1st week, the mean albumin was 3.5±0.50mg/dl, at 6th week it was 3.6±0.52mg/dl and mean of 3.6±0.58mg/dl at 24th week. At the time of presentation, mean albumin and globulin ratio was 1.02±0.33 and it was improved to 1.09±0.44 at 24th week of follow-up. Majority 68 (34%) had periosteal thickening and most 51 (25.5%) had soft tissue swelling, lytic lesions in 20 (10%) patients, 25 (12.5%) had trabecular bone, 21 (10.5%) had sequestrum or sclerotic bone and 15 (7.5%) irregular joint surface was observed. Amongst them, 21 patients required ultrasonography, and in 13 (61.9%) soft tissue changes were observed and 08 (38.1%) had fluid accumulation in joint. Staph aureus was the most common organism which was found in 95%

of the patients. CT scan was done in 14 (07%) patients and MRI in 21 (34.5%) patients. Bone scan was advised and performed in 69 (34.5%) patients and most 83 (41.5%) had biopsy and later histopathological study. We did curettage and drainage in 33 (30%) patients and majority 167 (70%) did not require curettage and drainage treatment. Sequestrectomy was performed in 18 (09%) patients and 02 (01%) were treated with sequestrectomy with antibiotics beads. Flap coverage was not required in single case.

Out of the total 200 patients, we treated 105 (52.5%) patients with external fixator, 03 (1.5%) amongst 18 had sequestrectomy with segment transport, and only 2 (01%) patients required sequestrectomy, primary

compression and limb lengthening. Ankle foot orthosis (AFO) was given in 05 (2.5%) patients, 03 (1.5%) has knee ankle foot orthosis (KAFO) and only 01 (0.5%) had wrist brace as orthosis post-operatively. Cast was applied in 39 (19.5%) patients and majority 161 (80.5%) didn't require cast. Majority 178 (89%) had normal wound condition and 22 (11%) had wound discharge. Amongst the total 22 patients with discharge, 11 (50%) had serous discharge, 01 (0.5%) had serogenous, 07 (31.8%) had purulent and 03 (13.6%) had mix discharge from the wound. Majority 178 (89%) had normal range of motion (ROM) and 22 (11%) had restricted ROM. Amongst 123 cases, majority 112 (56%) had union achieved at fracture and 11 (8.9%) had non-union.

Complications of the various treatment was noted, and 03

Table 1. Demographic data of the patients

Variables	Frequency N=200	Percentage (%)
Gender of the Patient		
Male	172	86
Females	28	14
Smokers		
Yes	59	29.5
No	141	70.5
Addiction		
Yes	22	11
No	178	89
Age Mean(Years)±S.D	35.78±17-year	
Weight of the patients		
Under-weight	03	1.5
Normal weight	127	63.5
Over weight	53	26.5
Obese	17	18.5
Associated Disease		
Diabetes mellitus	44	22
Hypertension	11	5.5
Bronchial Asthma	01	0.5
IHD	10	05
No-comorbidities	136	68
Trauma		
Open Fracture	127	63.5
Close fracture	73	36.5
History of Operation		
Yes	139	69.5
No	61	29.5
Previous Investigation		
Yes	28	14
No	172	86
Type of Infection		
Nosocomial infection	66	33
Traumatic	36	18
Hematogenous	98	49
Height, weight and BMI (Mean±SD)	5.25±0.48fet, 60.28±12.9kg, 23.64±4.35 kg/m²	

Table 2: Antibiotics prescribed to the patients

Drugs Given to the patients	Frequency N=200	Percentage (%)
Ceftrizone	96	48%
Amikacyin sulphate	73	36.5%
Gentamycin	34	17%
Co-Amoxiclave	83	41.5%
Cefixime	84	42%
Clindamycin	42	21%
Fusidic Acid	51	25.5%

(1.5%) has limb length discrepancy, 04 (2%) had deformity. Amongst the 22 patients with stiffness disability was noted in 13 (6.5%) patients and joint contracture in 9 (3.5%) patients and 171 (85.5%) patients had no operative complications. We assessed the final outcome with scoring system and found excellent results in 29 (14.5%) patients, good in 59 (29.5%), fair in 71 (35.5%) and poor in 41 (20.5%) patients.

DISCUSSION

Osteo-articular infection has transitioned due to various factors including new causative organism, and antibiotic resistance to existing organisms.¹¹ Determining the treatment outcome in osteomyelitis is a challenge due to various reasons including heterogeneous nature of the infections and prolonged treatment with longer follow-ups. This belief has association with the fact of relapse of staphylococcus aureus as a causative agent of osteomyelitis which are far less frequent today due to improved antibiotic and surgical therapy. Currently, a 12-month follow-up after therapy is considered necessary to evaluate new antibiotics, pursuant to the joint Food and Drug Administration (FDA)/Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) guidelines published in 1992.¹²

The mean age of the patients in our study was 35.78±17-year with minimum age was three years and maximum age was 80 years. Hematogenous osteomyelitis is predominantly reported in age between 4 to 12 years¹³ and adolescent and young adults have been frequently associated with osteomyelitis due to primary infection.¹⁴ This could be the reason of road traffic accident that can result into open fracture in adults in this study.

There were 172 (86%) males and 28 (14%) females patients in our study who presented with osteo-articular infection. In our study, male population was high. The male to female ratio was 8.1. Data also reported that male have increased risk of infection than female. Osteo-articular infection peaks in childhood and adolescence and relatively decreases in adult age. In literature, male are effect two times more than females.^{15,16} Males are generally more prone to trauma which is a leading cause in Osteoarticular infections. For those patients with infected implants leading to bone infection, mainstay of treatment was found to be removal of implant,

debridement of wounds and removal of sequestered bone followed by an extensive antibiotic course for elimination of disease.

Staph. aureus was the most common causative organism in our study. It was found in 95% of the cases. The literature reported Staph. aureus as most common organism in osteomyelitis in 70% to 90% of the cases. It is also most common causative organism of cellulitis, septic arthritis, and abscess.^{17,18} Surgery along with antibiotics has vital role in management of osteomyelitis and septic arthritis in children.^{19,22} In our study, only 18 (9%) patients had simple sequestrectomy and 02 (01%) were treated with sequestrectomy with antibiotics beads. Flap coverage was not required in a single case.

Amongst the total 200 cases, we treated patients with different antibiotics including ceftriaxone in 96 (48%) patients, Amikacin sulphate in 73 (36.5%) patients, Gentamicin in 34 (17%), Co-Amoxiclav in 83(41.5%), cefixime in 84 (42%), 42 Clindamycin in (21%), and fusidic acid 51 (25.5%). Literature supports our method of microbiology and treatment regimen. According to the British Orthopedic Surgery and British Society for Children's Orthopaedic Surgery (BSCOS) guidelines, treatment with cephalosporin had good outcomes.^{23,24}

We assessed the final outcome with scoring system and found excellent results in 29 (14.5%) patients, good in 59 (29.5%), fair in 71 (35.5%) and poor in 41 (20.5%) patients.

Our study had limitation of case series with small sample size without randomization and it was single centered.

CONCLUSION

Most cases are post-traumatic, and Staphylococcus aureus is the most common organism found. Males are affected more than females due to increased incidence of trauma. Chronic Osteomyelitis is more prevalent than acute. Pus culture and sensitivity is the investigation of choice for all cases helping in early diagnosis. Intravenous antibiotics for at least 07 days followed by 02 weeks of oral antibiotics is the treatment of choice for all osteoarticular infections. Moreover, sequestrectomy followed by antibiotic therapy is the treatment of choice in chronic osteoarticular infection. Arthrotomy and curettage, wound debridement, removal of infected

implant and/or exchange with external fixator in addition to specific antibiotics improved outcomes. In most of the cases with osteomyelitis managed with these treatments can achieve good-to-excellent results.

REFERENCES

1. Canale S, Beaty H. Campbell's Operative Orthopedics. 12 ed: Elsevier Inc.; 2012.
2. Ross JJ. Septic arthritis. *Infect Dis Clin North Am.* 2005 Dec;19(4):799–817.
3. Morrissy RT, Haynes DW. Acute hematogenous osteomyelitis: a model with trauma as an etiology. *J Pediatr Orthop.* 1989 Jul;9(4):447–56.
4. Trampuz A, Zimmerli W. Diagnosis and treatment of implant-associated septic arthritis and osteomyelitis. *Curr Infect Dis Rep.* 2008 Sep;10(5):394–403.
5. Murillo O, Grau I, Lora-Tamayo J, Gomez-Junyent J, Ribera A, Tubau F, et al. The changing epidemiology of bacteraemic osteoarticular infections in the early 21st century. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2015 Mar;21(3):254.e1–8.
6. Zimmerli W, Trampuz A, Ochsner PE. Prosthetic-joint infections. *N Engl J Med.* 2004 Oct 14;351(16):1645–54.
7. Eckardt JJ, Wirganowicz PZ, Mar T. An aggressive surgical approach to the management of chronic osteomyelitis. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 1994 Jan;(298):229–39.
8. Faust SN, Clark J, Pallett A, Clarke NMP. Managing bone and joint infection in children. *Arch Dis Child.* 2012 Jun;97(6):545–53.
9. Masterson EL, Masri BA, Duncan CP. Treatment of infection at the site of total hip replacement. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery.* 1997 Nov 1;79(11):1740.
10. Sculco TP. The economic impact of infected joint arthroplasty. *Orthopedics.* 1995 Sep;18(9):871–3.
11. Lew DP, Waldvogel FA. Osteomyelitis. *N Engl J Med.* 1997 Apr 3;336(14):999–1007.
12. Calandra GB, Norden C, Nelson JD, Mader JT. Evaluation of new anti-infective drugs for the treatment of selected infections of the skin and skin structure. *Clinical infectious diseases.* 1992 Nov 1;15(Supplement_1):S148-54.
13. Barberán J. Management of infections of osteoarticular prosthesis. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2006;12:93–101.
14. Kumar P, Clark M. *Clinical Medicine.* 8 ed. London: WB: Saunders;. 2005;6.
15. King SM, Laxer RM, Manson D, Gold R. Chronic recurrent multifocal osteomyelitis: a noninfectious inflammatory process. *Pediatr Infect Dis J.* 1987 Oct;6(10):907–11.
16. Sharff KA, Richards EP, Townes JM. Clinical management of septic arthritis. *Curr Rheumatol Rep.* 2013 Jun;15(6):332.
17. Ryan MJ, Kavanagh R, Wall PG, Hazleman BL. Bacterial joint infections in England and Wales: analysis of bacterial isolates over a four year period. *Br J Rheumatol.* 1997 Mar;36(3):370–3.
18. Gupta MN, Sturrock RD, Field M. A prospective 2 year study of 75 patients with adult onset septic arthritis. *Rheumatology [Internet].* 2001; Available from: <https://academic.oup.com/rheumatology/article-abstract/40/1/24/1783948>
19. Pääkkönen M, Peltola H. Simplifying the treatment of acute bacterial bone and joint infections in children. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther.* 2011 Dec;9(12):1125–31.
20. Agarwal A, Aggarwal AN. Bone and Joint Infections in Children: Acute Hematogenous Osteomyelitis. *Indian J Pediatr.* 2016 Aug;83(8):817–24.
21. Pääkkönen M, Peltola H. Management of a child with suspected acute septic arthritis. *Arch Dis Child.* 2012 Mar;97(3):287–92.
22. Kang SN, Sanghera T, Mangwani J, Paterson JMH, Ramachandran M. The management of septic arthritis in children: systematic review of the English language literature. *J Bone Joint Surg Br.* 2009 Sep;91(9):1127–33.
23. Iliadis AD, Ramachandran M. Paediatric bone and joint infection. *EFORT Open Rev.* 2017 Jan;2(1):7–12.
24. El-Sayed AMM. Treatment of early septic arthritis of the hip in children: comparison of results of open arthrotomy versus arthroscopic drainage. *J Child Orthop.* 2008 Jun;2(3):229–37.